

HUMANITY SPACE
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МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ АЛЬМАНАХ

2025

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TYPUS

Tienmuschan
N.W.China Rtt.

Glenea
tienmushana
n.
Det. Dr. Heyrovský

HOLOTYPUS
Glenea
TIENMUSHANA
Heyrovsky, 1939

Зоомузей МГУ (Москва, РОССИЯ)
№ ZMMU Col 03006
Zool. Mus. Mosq. Univ.
(Mosquae, ROSSIA)
ex coll. N. N. Plavilstshikov

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Two new subspecies of *Alosterna tabacicolor* (DeGeer, 1775) (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) from the Far East of Russia

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Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Lepturinae, *Alosterna tabacicolor*, new subspecies, Russian Far East.

Abstract. *Alosterna tabacicolor kompantsevi* **ssp. n.** from Kunashir Is. and *A. t. toyohara* **ssp. n.** from South Sakhalin Is. are described. Both subspecies are close to *A. t. erythropus* (Gebler, 1841) and *A. t. tenebris* Danilevsky, 2012 (both from mainland Asia) as well as to *A. t. sachalinensis* Danilevsky, 2012 from northern Sakhalin Is. and to *A. t. hirayamai* Fujita, 2018 from the central of Japanese Honshu Is. The distinguishing characters and color illustrations are proposed.

Introduction

The reason for the present article was the publication by Fujita, Hirayama & Akita (2018: 21, 25, 224, Tab. 67, figs 121: 5-7) of *A. tabacicolor fusca* Matsushita, 1930 as a valid name from Rishiri Island, Hokkaido Is., Kuril Iss (Kunashir Is.) and Honshu Is. (Aomori Prefecture). In fact the name is unavailable, as it was shown by Danilevsky (2011: 315): it was introduced as *Alosterna tabacicolor* var. *fusca* Matsushita, 1930 (Mt. Kurodake, Hokkaido) together with *Alosterna tabacicolor* var. *bivittis*: Matsushita, 1930 (Mt. Kurodake, Hokkaido) - two variations from one locality, so “its author expressly gave it infrasubspecific rank” according to the Article 45.6.4. of ICZN (1999). So, the subspecies distributed from Hokkaido to Kunashir needs a new name, which is proposed bellow.

A. tabacicolor (DeGeer, 1775) is distributed all over the north of Palaearctic Region from Spain to Japan, but its geographical variability is not investigated good enough. Only 8 subspecies are already described: *A. t. tabacicolor* from Europe; rather variable *A. t. erythropus* Gebler, 1841(= *bivittis* Motschulsky, 1860) from

M.L. Danilevsky

Siberia with often dark to black elytra; rather variable *A. t. subvittata* Reitter, 1885 (= *caucasica* Plavilstshikov, 1936) from Caucasus with often dark elytra; *A. t. azerbaijanica* Danilevsky, 2014 with black elytra from North-East Azerbaijan; *A. t. tokatensis* Pic, 1901 from Turkey, Tokat; *A. t. tenebris* Danilevsky, 2012 with black elytra from Russian Primorie, Korea and northern China; *A. t. sakhalinensis* Danilevsky, 2012 with dark elytra from northern Sakhalin; *A. t. hirayamai* Fujita, 2018 with dark elytra from central Honshu, Japan.

Acronyms of collections.

MD - collection of M.L. Danilevsky (Moscow, Russia);

ML - collection of M.A. Lazarev (Moscow, Russia).

Results

Alosterna tabacicolor kompantsevi ssp. n.

Figs 1-2

Allosterna tabacicolor bivittis, Plavilstshikov, 1936: 306, part. - Siberia, all of Sakhalin, Japan; Krivolutsкая, 1973: 99, part. - Kunashir, Iturup, Shikotan, Japan (Hokkaido, Honshu, Shikoku, Kyushu).

Allosterna tabacicolor var. *fusca* Matsushita, 1930: 24 - Hokkaido.

Allosterna tabacicolor ab. *bivittis*, Tsherepanov, 1979: 239.

Alosterna tabacicolor, Kusama & Takakuwa, 1984: 201, part. - Japan, Kunashir; Ohbayashi N. 2007: 390.

Alosterna tabacicolor bivittis, Tsherepanov, 1996: 80, part. - Siberia, Far East Russia, Sakhalin, Kunashir, Iturup, Shikotan, Japan (Hokkaido, Honshu).

Alosterna tabacicolor erythropus Danilevsky & Smetana, 2010: 96, part. - Siberia, Far East Russia, Japan; Danilevsky, 2020: 120, part. - Siberia, Far East Russia, Japan.

Alosterna tabacicolor fusca, Fujita, Hirayama & Akita, 2018: 27, 224-225 (unavailable name) - Rishiri Island, Hokkaido, Kuril Islands (Kunashir Island) and Honshu (Aomori Prefecture).

Type locality. Kunashir island, Mendeleevo.

Description. Body and prothorax relatively longer than in specimens from the mainland; elytra usually pale, with bigger and denser punctation; light specimens dominate in all populations, though rare black specimens are also known; the area along elytral suture, elytral

M.L. Danilevsky

margins and elytral apices are more or less darkened; 1st antennal joint and legs are pale; body length of available specimens, males: 6,6-7,8 mm, female 7,0 mm; width in males: 1,8-1,9 mm, in female: 2,0 mm; body length of “*A. t. fusca*” (sensu Fujita et al., 2018): 6,7-9,4 mm.

Differential diagnosis. The taxon is close to usually very dark *A. t. hirayamai* Fujita, 2018, but most of known specimens are much lighter, though several dark specimens are also known.

Material. Holotype, male, Russia, Kunashir Is., Mendeleevo, 10.7.1977, A. Kompantsev leg. - MD; 5 paratypes; 3 males, 1 female, Russia, Kunashir Is., Tretyakovo, 17.7.1977, A. Kompantsev leg. - MD; 1 female, Japan, Hokkaido, 5.VII.1931, K. Kobayashi leg. - ML.

Distribution. In Russia the taxon is known from Kunashir Is. only. It is widely distributed in Hokkaido, recorded from Rishiri Is., but also known from Honshu Is. (Aomori Prefecture).

Alosterna tabacicolor toyohara ssp. n.

Figs 3-10

Alosterna tabacicolor bivittis, Plavilstshikov, 1936: 306, part. - Siberia, all of Sakhalin, Japan.

Alosterna tabacicolor ab. *bivittis*, Tsherepanov, 1979: 239.

Alosterna tabacicolor bivittis, Tsherepanov, 1996: 80, part. - Siberia, Far East Russia, Sakhalin, Kunashir, Iturup, Shikotan, Japan (Hokkaido, Honshu).

Alosterna tabacicolor erythropus Danilevsky & Smetana, 2010: 96, part. - Siberia, Far East Russia, Japan; Danilevsky, 2020: 120, part. - Siberia, Far East Russia, Japan.

Type locality. Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk environs, southern Sakhalin.

Description. Body and prothorax relatively longer than in *A. t. hirayamai* Fujita, 2018 from Central Honshu (Japan); elytra usually pale in anterior third (about a half of the type series), with smaller and sparser punctation; only 2 males are light along most of elytral surface (darkened laterally and apically); only 1 male with totally black elytra; 1st antennal joint, legs and abdominal apex are always pale; body length in males: 5.7-8.0 mm, width: 1,5-1,9 mm; body length in females: 6,7-6,8 mm, width: 1,7-1,9 mm

M.L. Danilevsky

Material. Holotype, male, Russia, southern Sakhalin Is., Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk env., 24.6.1985, M. Danilevsky - MD; 26 paratypes: 22 males, 1 female with same data - MD; 1 male, southern Sakhalin Is., Kuznetsova cape, 14.6.1985, M. Danilevsky - MD; 1 male, 1 female, southern Sakhalin Is., Anna cape, 26.7.1976, V. Kuznetsov leg. - MD.

Differential diagnosis. The taxon is not close to dark *A. t. sakhalinensis* Danilevsky, 2012 distributed from central to north Sakhalin. It is very similar to rather distant Japanese *A. t. hirayamai* Fujita, 2018 distributed in Central Honshu, by differs by more elongated body with smaller and sparser punctuation.

Distribution. The taxon is distributed in south Sakhalin only.

Specimens used for comparison.

A. t. erythropus (Gebler, 1841) (= *bivittis* Motschulsky, 1860): 1 male, 1 female, Russia, Tuva Republic, Ishtii-Khem, 17.6.1972, M. Danilevsky leg. - MD; 11 males, 2 females, with same data - ML; 1 male, same locality, 20.6.1979 - MD; 1 male (with black elytra and black 1st antennal joint), Russia, Bratsk env., Angara River, 2-3.7.2006, D. Fominykh leg., - MD; 2 males, Russia, Khabarovsk region, Komsomolsky natural reserve, Gur river valley, 2.9.1975 (ex larvae from *Maackia amurensis*, 1.9.1976), M. Danilevsky - MD; 2 males, Russia, Khabarovsk region, Solnechnyi environs, Gornyi, 1992, A. Shadenkov leg. - MD.

A. t. hirayamai Fujita, 2018: 2 paratypes, 1 male, Pass Ogawara (ca. 2000 m alt.) Saku City, Nagano Pref., Honshu Is., Japan, 16.7.2014, H. Hirayama leg. - MD; 1 female, Pass Kitazawa (1980-2200 m alt.), Hase-mura, Nagano Pref., Honshu Is., Japan, 30.7.1985, H. Hirayama leg. - MD; 1 female, Yatsugatake, Shinshu, Honshu Is., Japan, 29.7.1938, Y. Chiura leg. - ML.

A. t. tenebris Danilevsky, 2012: holotype, male with the label: Russia, Primorsky Region, Kamenushka [43°37'N, 132°14'E], 2.6.1960, K. Stepanov leg. - MD; 6 paratypes: 1 male and 5 females, South Korea, Mt. Jiri, Samsinbong, 17.6.1994, T. Ueno leg. - MD; 2 males, 1 female, Russia, Vladivostok, plant garden, 14.6.2018, A. Shamaev leg. - MD; 2 males, 1 female, Russia, Primorsky Region, Lazovsky range, Lazovsky Mt., 10.7.2015, S. Ivanov leg. -

M.L. Danilevsky

MD; 2 females, Russia, Primorsky Region, 30 km NW Arseniev, 30.5.-4.6.2021, S. Ivanov leg. - MD.

A. t. sakhalinensis Danilevsky, 2012: holotype, male, Russia, northern Sakhalin Is., 45km SE Tymovsk, 50°39'N, 143°13'E, 19.7.2010, A.Zubov leg. - MD; 4 paratypes, females with same label - MD; 7 males 1 female, Sakhalin Is., Tymovsk environs, Diatlov stream, 50°51'18"N, 143°18'27"E, 290 m, 12.07.2010, A. Zubov leg. - MD; 1 male, Sakhalin Is., Tymovsk environs, Langari, 50°31'17"N, 142°43'40"E, 175 m, 24.06.2010, A. Zubov leg. - MD; 3 males, Sakhalin Is., Tymovsk environs, Chamginsky Pass, 50°44'40"N, 143°18'16"E, 1430 m, 1-3.06.2010, A. Zubov leg. - MD; 1 female, Sakhalin Is., Tymovsk environs, Oven river mouth, 50°40'16"N, 143°18'16"E, 340 m, 10.07. 2010, A. Zubov leg. - MD; 1 male, northern Sakhalin, Shmidta peninsula, 24.08.1973, Ivliev, Kononov leg. - MD.

Etymology. *Alosterna tabacicolor kompatsevi* **ssp. n.** is dedicated to my late colleague Alexander Kompantsev, who collected the type series many years ago. *A. t. toyohara* **ssp. n.** is named after old Japanese name of Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk - Toyohara.

Acknowledgement. I am very grateful to Maxim Lazarev (Free Economic Society of Russia, Moscow), who supplied me with several interesting specimens.

Figs 1-10. *Alosterna tabacicolor* from far east islands of Russia:

Figs 1-2. *A. t. kompantsevi* ssp. n.: 1. holotype, male; 2. paratype, female, Russia, Kunashir Is., Tretyakovo, 17.7.1977, A. Kompantsev leg.

Figs 3-10. *A. t. toyohara* ssp. n.: 3. holotype, male; 4-8. paratypes, males with same label; 9-10. paratypes, females with same label.

M.L. Danilevsky

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M.L. Danilevsky

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A description of the male of *Globicornis (Hadrotoma) semilimbata* (Pic, 1906) (Coleoptera: Dermestidae: Megatominae)

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Key words: Coleoptera, Dermestidae, taxonomy, faunistics, Greece, Macedonia.

Abstract. The male of *Globicornis (Hadrotoma) semilimbata* (Pic, 1906) is described, illustrated, commented and newly recorded from Macedonia.

Introduction

The aim of the present paper is to describe the morphology of the male of *Globicornis (Hadrotoma) semilimbata*. So far only a single female of the taxon, the holotype, has been described, which was collected in Greece and described by Pic in 1906.

The species was originally described in the genus *Hadrotoma*. Mroczkowski (1968) transferred the species to the genus *Globicornis* subgenus *Hadrotoma* as *Globicornis (Hadrotoma) corticalis* var. *semilimbata*. Háva (2007) stated it as valid species *G. (H.) semilimbata*.

In this work, the description of the species *Globicornis (Hadrotoma) semilimbata* is supplemented with a description of the male characteristics.

Materials and methods

The size of the beetles or of their body parts can be useful in species recognition and thus, the following measurements were made (in mm):

total length (TL) - linear distance from anterior margin of pronotum to apex of elytra.

elytral width (EW) - maximum linear transverse distance.

J. Háva

Photographs were made with a Canon EOS 550 D camera, and the images were modified with Helicon Focus 7.7.5. software.

Acronyms of material depositories:

JHAC - collection of Jiří Háva (Únětice u Prahy, Prague-West, Czech Republic);

JSPC - collection of Jiří Stanovský (Ostrava; Czech Republic);

MNHN - collection of Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle (Paris, France);

RSPC - collection of Rudolf Schuh (Katzelsdorf, Austria).

Results

Globicornis (Hadrotoma) semilimbata (Pic, 1906)

Figs 1-8

Hadrotoma corticalis var. *semilimbata* Pic, 1906: 9.

Globicornis corticalis var. *semilimbata*, Mroczkowski, 1968: 115.

Globicornis semilimbata, Háva, 2007: 57.

Original description of female holotype by Pic (1906): “Foncé, ave cle pourtour externe des élytres et une étroite bordure suturale postérieure roussâtre, tibias et tarses roux. Grèce: Sudena en Morée (ex Holtz).”

Description of male. Body slightly convex, elongated (Fig. 4), measurements: TL 3.6-4.0 mm, EW 1.8-2.0 mm. Dorsal and ventral parts covered by recumbent, yellow setation.

Head visible from above; integument of head is dark-brown; densely punctured. Eyes large, and convex without internal emargination. Median ocellus is present. Antenna has 10 antennomeres (Fig. 5). Antennal club with three antennomeres. Terminal antennomere in male (Fig. 5), in female is short and triangular. All antennomeres brown and are covered with erect brown setation. Palpomeres brown.

Pronotum dark-brown, coarsely punctured; medially with two depressions (Fig. 6). Posterior parts slightly dentate. Pronotal dorsal

J. Háva

rim of antennal fossa of male slightly visible from above, while in female it is less visible.

Scutellum small, triangular with large punctures.

Elytra brown in first 1/3 laterally with reddish fascia (Fig. 2); entire area is sparsely punctured and covered by brown setation. Epipleuron brown with yellow setation.

Abdominal ventrites I-V with surfaces of integument dark-brown, finely punctured, and covered by yellow setation.

Legs brown with short yellow setation.

Pygidium brown, with short yellow setation.

Male genitalia (Fig. 7).

Type material. Holotype (♀): „Sudená, Morea, Holtz“ [= Kalavryta] / „Type“ / „TYPE“ / „H. corticalis v. semilimbata Pic“ - MNHN.

Material examined: 1 ♂, 4 ♀♀, Greece, Peloponnes: Ilia, Erymanthos mts. (S), 1.5 km NNW Orini, 1290-1370 m, 9.5.2013, Schuh lgt., J. Háva det. - RSPC, JHAC; 1 ♂, Greece, Peloponnesos, 40 km SE Tripoli, Umg. Agios Petros, 900-1160 m, 22.iii.1997, V. Assing lgt., - JHAC; 2 ♀♀, GR, Pelop. m., Mt. Taigetos, Poliana, 17-18.6.1974, Horák+Švihla lgt., J. Háva det. - JHAC; 1 ♀, Greece, S Kozani, Livadero env., 15.5.2014, Snížek lgt. - JHAC; 1 ♀, Greece, Western Macedonia, 4 km NW of Deskati, 1500 m, 39°56'N 21°46'E, 1.6.2015, O. Konvička lgt. - JHAC; 1 ♀, GR, Ioánina, Notia Pindos Mts., 1420 m, Metsovo env., meadows, 13.6.2012, B. Zbuzek lgt., - JHAC; 1 ♀, Greece, Macedonia, Mt. Trikláριο, 7 km N of Andartikó, 40°47.52'N 21°14.3'E, 1540 m, 1.6.2007, P. Kabátek lgt. - JHAC; 1 ♀, Greece, Pel., Alonistaina env., 1200-1400 m, 37°39'N, 22°12'E, 1-5.6.2009, Zd. Švec lgt. - JHAC; 2 spec., Macedonia, Bistra planina, Lazaropole, 1348 m, 22.5.2017, J. Stanovský lgt., J. Háva det. - JSPC, JHAC.

Differential diagnosis. The species is very similar to *G. (H.) corticalis* (Eichhoff, 1863) but differs from it by the reddish anterolateral elytral fascia, structure of antennae and male genitalia.

Distribution. A species known only from Greece, new to Macedonia. Háva & Herrmann (2017) erroneously recorded it from Croatia.

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Figs 1-3. *Globicornis (Hadrotoma) semilimbata* (Pic, 1906), holotype (♀): 1. habitus, dorsal aspect; 2. habitus, lateral aspect; 3. holotype labels.

Figs 4-8. *Globicornis (Hadrotoma) semilimbata* (Pic, 1906): 4. habitus of male, dorsal aspect; 5. antenna of male; 6. pronotum; 7. male genitalia; 8. female antennal club.

J. Háva

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Two subspecies names of *Rhagium inquisitor* (Linnaeus, 1758) from Central Europe and North America (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) are restored

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Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, taxonomy, zoogeography, restored name.

Abstract. *Rhagium inquisitor lineatum* (Olivier, 1795), **rest. nom.** and *Rh. i. sudeticum* Plavilstshikov, 1936, **rest. nom.** (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) are proposed as valid names.

Introduction

The genus includes several similar taxa from Europe, Asia, Africa and North America. European taxa are still regarded as one species *Rhagium inquisitor*. Many local populations from all over North America were originally described as different species.

Now all American names are paradoxally accepted (Bezark, 2025) as synonyms of the nominative subspecies *Rh. i. inquisitor* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Figs 1-2) described from West Europe. Unfortunately, the adequate taxonomy of American *Rh. inquisitor* needs careful study of local materials, which are not in my disposal. Rather probably many American names could be revalidated at species level, but now I preliminary propose the oldest American name for all - *Rh. i. lineatum* (Olivier, 1795), **rest. nom.** The name was accepted as valid by Podaný (1964) for N. Amerika and Canada: British Columbia, Alberta, Manitoba, Quebec, Ontario, N. Scotland, Oregon, California, Idaho, Arizona, Colorado, New York, Massachusetts, Alaska, New Mexico.

Variability of European populations is poorly investigated. In fact, it is not less than American. Only Far East populations of

M.A. Lazarev

Rhagium sensu Lazarev 2024 were more or less adequately accepted as several species.

Materials and methods

All photographs were taken with Canon PowerShot G10 digital camera equipped with Cannon Zoom lens 5X IS 6.1-30.5 mm 1:2.8-4.5. The illustrations were edited with Adobe Photoshop 7.0 and Helicon Focus 3.20.

Acronyms of collections:

MD - collection of M.L. Danilevsky (Moscow, Russia);

ML - collection of M.A. Lazarev (Moscow, Russia).

Results

Genus *Rhagium* Fabricius, 1775

Rhagium Fabricius, 1775: 182; 1776: 51; Olivier, 1791: 367; Stephens, 1831: 253; Audinet-Serville, 1835: 205; Westwood, 1839: 41; Curtis, 1839: 750; Blanchard, 1845: 164; Haldeman, 1847: 58; LeConte, 1850b: 319; 1854: 219; 1874: 190; Emmons, 1854: 125; Schiødte, 1865: 205; Chenu, 1870: 330; Redtenbacher, 1874: 428; LeConte & Horn, 1883: 313; Bates, 1885: 277; Leng, 1890: 65; Wickham, 1897a: 88; Blatchley, 1910: 1046, 1048; Schaufuß, 1916: 827; Boppe, 1921: 37; Craighead, 1923: 83; Planet, 1924: 107; Portevin, 1927: 18; Picard, 1929: 66; Winkler, 1929: 1146; Böving & Craighead, 1931: pl. 99 (figs G, H); Arnett, 1962: 857, 877; Chemsak, 1964: 234; 2005: 33, 118; Podaný, 1964: 5; Hansen, 1966: 70; Hatch, 1971: 124; Linsley & Chemsak, 1972: 84; Mamaev & Danilevsky, 1975: 108, 112 (larva); Bílý & Mehl, 1989: 35; Bense, 1995: 41, 111; Monné, 1995: 30; Sama, 2003: 12; Silfverberg, 2004: 76; Tamutis et al., 2011: 316; Sama & Rapuzzi, 2011: 128; Berger, 2012: 81; Švácha & Lawrence, 2014: 153, 156; Haack & al., 2017: 84; Bousquet & al., 2017: 104; Bouchard & al., 2024: 465; Özdikmen, 2024: 2704, 2706 (sensu Lazarev, 2024).

Hargium Leach, 1819: 210, type species: *Cerambyx inquisitor* Linnaeus, 1758.

Allorhagium Kolbe, 1884: 270, type species: *Cerambyx inquisitor* Linnaeus, 1758.

Rhagium (*Allorhagium* Semenov, 1898: 601), unjustified amendment.

Rhagium (*Hargium*), Aurivillius, 1912: 164; Harde, 1966: 19, part.; Kaszab, 1971: 42, part.

Harpium (s. str.) Reitter, 1913: 7, misspelling (unavailable name).

Rhagium (*Hargium* department *Hargium*), Plavilstshikov, 1932: 93.

Rhagium (*Hargium* skupina *Hargium*), Heyrovský, 1955: 76, part.

M.A. Lazarev

Rhagium (*Hargium* sect. *Hargium*), Plavilstshikov, 1915: 34; 1936: 133, 504; Panin & Săvulescu, 1961: 84.

Stenocorus (s. str.), Gressitt, 1951: 54.

Rhagium (*Allorhagium*), Planet, 1924: 109; Portevin, 1927: 19; Gressitt, 1953: 207

Stenocorus, Geoffroy, 1762: 221; Olivier, 1795: (69) 1, part.; Lamarck, 1817: 312; Thomson, 1861: 144, 156; 1864: 144, 409; Lacordaire, 1868: 428; LeConte, 1873: 328; Provancher, 1877: 580, 605; Swaine & Hopping, 1928: 12, 14; Bradley, 1930: 235; Chagnon, 1936: 244; Hopping, 1937: 9; Knull, 1946: 151, 173; Dillon & Dillon, 1961: 618; Chagnon & Robert, 1962: 241, 244.

Rhagium (s. str.), Aurivillius 1912: 161; Planet, 1924: 111; Portevin, 1927: 18; Villiers, 1978: 79; Lobanov & al., 1981: 795; Danilevsky & Miroshnikov, 1985: 123; Bílý & Mehl, 1989: 38; Švácha, 1989: 54 (larva); Pesarini & Sabbadini, 1994: 14; Althoff & Danilevsky, 1997: 9; Vives, 2000: 215; Martynov & Pisarenko, 2004: 47; Bartenev, 2004: 25; 2009: 40; N.Ohbayashi, 2007: 352; Danilevsky & Smetana, 2010: 132; Özdikmen & Turgut, 2010: 967; Danilevsky, 2014: 86; Danilevsky, 2020: 175.

Type species: *Cerambyx inquisitor* Linnaeus, 1758

Prothorax with big lateral protuberances and with a long and wide intercoxal process reaching hind coxal cavities; each elytron with 2-3 distinct carinae; antennae short, surpassing elytral bases; temples shining, much shorter than eyes; slightly protruding laterally; each elytron with two diffused pale belts.

The circumpolar genus includes 9 species.

***Rhagium inquisitor* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Cerambyx inquisitor Linnaeus (= Linné), 1758: 393 - "Europa"; 1761: 190; 1767: 630 - "Europa"; Poda, 1761: 33 "ad Graecium"; Schrank, 1781: 136 - Austria.

Cerambyx nubeculus Bergsträsser, 1778: 26 - "in der Grafschaft Hanau-Münzenberg".

Rhagium inquisitor, Fabricius, 1781: 229 - "Europae truncis arborum"; 1787: 145 - "Germania"; 1793: 304 - "Europae truncis arborum"; Fabricius, 1802: 313 - "Europa"; Schönherr, 1817: 412 - "Europa"; Audinet-Serville, 1835: 206 - "Environs de Paris"; Castelnau, 1840: 500 - "France, Suisse"; Küster, 1848: 84 - "Vom nördlichen Europa durch die ganze Mitte bis Frankreich und Oberitalien"; Saalas, 1936: 70 - "Europa, Sibirien, Japan"; Reymond, 1953: 203 - "Maroc (Moyen-Atlas), Algérie (Djurdjura et Babor)"; Duffy, 1960: 74 - "Europe, Scotland, Siberia, North Africa, Japan"; Mulsant, 1863: 454, part.; Lindeman, 1871: 205, part.; Ganglbauer, 1882a: 718; 1882b: 40; Köenig, 1899: 393; Winkler, 1929: 1147, part.; Hayashi, 1960: 3; 1963: 129; Ilinsky, 1962: 301, larva; Krivolutskaya, 1965: 62; Plavilstshikov,

M.A. Lazarev

- 1965: 398; Paulus, 1969: 5, larva; Alekseev & Lurye 1970: 651, larva; Mamaev & Danilevsky, 1975: 114, larva; Tsherepanov, 1979: 77 part., larva, biology; Kadyrbekov & Tleppaeva, 1997: 41 - Almaty Nature Reserve; Danilevsky, 1982: 814, key to larvae of the genus; Krivosheina & Kompantsev, 1984: 169, biology; Sama, 1988: 7; Adlbauer, 1992: 489 - Turkey; Bense, 1995: 111; Pesarini & Sabbadini, 1995: 68 - "Europa, Africa settentrionale, Asia temperata, Nordamerica"; Grosso-Silva, 2000: 40 - "Portugal: Manteigas"; Warzee & Drumont, 2004: 49 - "Belgique"; Migliaccio & al., 2004: 140 - "Vitoshka Mountain, Bulgaria"; Micas, 2005: 148 - "vallón de la Moulière (Alpes-de-Haute-Provence)"; Rapuzzi & Sama, 2006: 160 - "Sicilia: Etna"; Brin & al., 2006: 60 - "vallée du Marcadau (Hautes-Pyrénées)"; Simon, 2007: 155 - "Domaine de Rochebois à Vitrac (Dordogne)"; Ehnström & Holmer, 2007: 22, 32, 55, 110 - Sweden, Denmark, Norway, Finland; Rousset, 2007: 46 - "forêt de Maubert, entre Saint-Amandin, Condat et Trémouille (Cantal)"; Dodelin & Sauvagère, 2009: 3 - "Haute-Normandie"; Berger & al., 2010: 21 - "Grèce : province de Ionnina, 7 km au nord de Konitsa"; Tamutis & al., 2011: 316 - Litva; Lindhe & al., 2011: 278, 279 - "Sweden"; Pacini, 2011: 15 - "Uzhgorod, the Carpathians, Ukraine"; Berger, 2012: 82; Dobrosavljević & Mihajlović, 2014: 24 - "Serbia"; Švácha & Lawrence, 2014, biology; Plewa & al., 2014: 128 - "Romania"; Lim & al., 2014: 131 - "Korea"; Choi & al., 2016: 239 - "South Korea"; Troukens & al., 2017: 14 - "omgeving van Brussel"; Żurawlew & Melke, 2018: 84 - "Poland: Pleszew District (Wielkopolska-Kujawy Lowland)"; Vitali, 2018: 73 - "Luxembourg"; Yalçın & al., 2020: 6 - "Northwest Turkey"; Dovhaniuk & Zamoroka, 2020: 134 - Ukraine (Ternopil Region): National Park "Kremenetski Hory"; Barševskis & al., 2021: 136 - "Latvia: Kinkausku forest, Celminiki"; Ruchin & et al., 2022: 17 - Central European Russia; Zamoroka, 2022: 55 - Ukraine; Saikina & al., 2022: 798 - Russia: Omsk Region; Trócoli & al., 2023: 243 - "España (Barcelona, Catalunya): Moianès"; Volovnik, 2024: 44 - "Southern Ukraine: Zaporizhia Oblast".
- Rhagium indagator* Fabricius, 1787: 145 - "Germania"; Gebler, 1830: 189 - Altay; 1848: 410 - "um Salair, im kusnezsk."; Mulsant, 1839: 227 - France; 1863: 456, part.; Küster, 1848: 85 - "Im nördlichen und mittleren Europa bis zum gemäßigten Süden häufig"; Motschulsky, 1859: 493 - "environs du fl. Amour, depuis la Schilka jusqu'à Nikolaëvsk"; 1860a: 310 - "Songarie"; 1860b: 149 - "Dans toute la Sibérie"; Lindeman, 1871: 205, part.
- Rhagium minutum* Fabricius, 1787: 146 - Germany: "Kiliae".
- Cerambyx (Rhagium) indagator*, Gmelin, 1790: 1845 - "Germania".
- Cerambyx (Rhagium) exilis* Gmelin, 1790: 1844.
- Cerambyx (Rhagium) inquisitor*, Gmelin, 1790: 1845 - "Europae truncis arborum"
- Stenocorus inquisitor*, Olivier, 1795: (69) 9; Lamarck, 1801: 235; 1817: 313; Gemminger, 1872: 2855; Schneider & Leder, 1879: 320 - "Suram" (= *indagator* F.); Baudi di Selve, 1889: 185 - Piemonte.
- Stenocorus indagator*, Olivier, 1795: (69) 12, part.
- Stenocorus minutus*, Olivier, 1795: (69) 15, part. - "en Allemagne".

M.A. Lazarev

- Leptura inquisitor*, Latreille, 1804: 307 - "toute l'Europe".
- Stenocorus cephalotes minor* Voet, 1806: 29, nomen nudum.
- Rhagium fortipes* Reitter, 1898: 357 - Turkey: Hatay.
- Allorhagium inquisitor*, Matsumura, 1911: 134, part. - "Japan, Amur, Europa".
- Rhagium (Hargium) inquisitor*, Aurivillius, 1912: 164 - "Europa, Sibirien, Japan; Schaufuß", 1916: 828 - "Fernere paläarktische Arten"; Villiers, 1946: 39 - "Algérie"; Heyrovský, 1955: 79; Panin & Sävulescu, 1961: 84; Kaszab, 1971: 44.
- Harpium* (s. str.) *inquisitor*, Reitter, 1913: 7.
- Rhagium Iberonis* Ericson, 1916: 240 - "Ibero".
- Rhagium (Allorhagium) inquisitor*, Peyerimhoff, 1919: 209 - "Babor, Djurdjura".
- Rhagium* (s. str.) *inquisitor*, Portevin, 1927: 19 - France; Villiers, 1978: 80; Lobanov & al., 1981: 795; Danilevsky & Miroschnikov, 1985: 125; Švácha, 1989: 54, 58, part., larva; Althoff & Danilevsky, 1997: 9; Vincent, 1998: 24 - "Ile de France"; Tozlu & al., 2002: 62 - Turkey; Sama, 2002: 12; Bartenev, 2004: 25, part.; 2009: 40, part.; Denux, 2005: 229, 236 - "Parc naturel régional du Perche (Orne & Eure-et-Loir)"; Berger & Peslier, 2014: 570 - "toute la France"; Facon, 2016: 8 - "France: Montreuillois"; Cartier & Cartier, 2016: 229 - "Vienne: Vouillé"; Klausnitzer & al., 2016: 337 - "Mitteleuropa"; Stolbov & al., 2019: 200 - Russia (Tyumenskaya Oblast); Alekseev & Maryutin, 2019: 6 - Russia (Kalouga); Özdikmen 2021a: 443 - Turkey; 2021b: 511 - Turkey; Bunalski & al., 2022: 12 - Western Poland.
- Rhagium (Hargium) inquisitor*, Plavilshnikov, 1932: 94.
- Rhagium (Hargium) inquisitor*, Plavilshnikov, 1936: 141, 504, part.
- Rhagium (Hargium) inquisitor*, G. Müller, 1949: 42.
- Rhagium (Hargium) inquisitor fortipes*, Podaný, 1964: 20 - "Akbés, Syrien", part.
- Rhagium inquisitor*, Kadyrbekov & al., 1996: 86, misspelling - Zailiysky Alatau on the Shrenk spruce (Medeo).
- Rhagium (Megarhagium) inquisitor*, Reisdorf & al., 2015: 155 - "Marais de Montabé (Essonne)".
- Rhagium* (s.str.) *inquisitor*, Şabanoğlu, 2020: 199, misspelling - "Turkey: Rize".

Type locality. "Europa" and rather probably Sweden (Tavakilian & Chevillotte, 2025).

Body moderately dark with distinct elytral carinae strongly developed; general body color from rather pale to nearly black; body length: 9.5-20.0 mm.

Distribution. North Asia (without Central Asia and Palestine), North America. North Africa and about whole Europe.

Bionomy. Larvae develop under the dead bark of various coniferous trees: *Pinus*, *Picea*, *Abies*, *Cedrus*, *Larix*, etc., but development on deciduous trees has also been frequently noted: *Betula* (especially in

M.A. Lazarev

Siberia), *Populus*, *Quercus*, *Fagus*; in Sweden *Alnus* is often infested (Palm, 1959); *Betula* has been noted to be populated in the Kostroma region (Krivosheina & Kompantsev, 1984). Pupation under the bark occurs at the end of summer; the imago overwinters. Adult beetles are active in spring and early summer, occasionally visiting flowers. Generation is 2 years.

***Rhagium inquisitor lineatum* (Olivier, 1795), rest. nom.**

Stenocorus lineatus Olivier, 1795: 13 - "Amérique"; Provancher, 1877: 605 - "Canada"; Doane & al., 1936: 170; Chagnon, 1936: 244 - "Province de Québec"; Kimmey & Furniss, 1943: 262, biology; Craighead, 1950: 262, biology - "Throughout United States"; Becker, 1955: 164, biology - "Massachusetts"; Clark, 1956: 41 - "near Terrace, British Columbia"; Townes & Townes, 1960: 140 - "America, north of Mexico"; Chagnon & Robert, 1962: 244 - "Québec".

Rhagium lineatum, Schönherr, 1817: 414 - "America"; Audinet-Serville, 1835: 207 - "Amérique du Nord"; Harris, 1838: 95 - "in Massachusetts"; 1841: 93 - "Massachusetts"; Haldeman, 1847: 58 - United States; LeConte, 1850a: 235; 1850b: 319 - "Maine to Chihuahua"; 1879: 505 - Alpine Rocky Mountain Regions; Melshimer, 1853: 112 - United States; Emmons, 1854: 126 - New York; Glover, 1869: 104, biology; Dimmock, 1871: 15; Packard, 1872: 501, biology; Fuller, 1875: 97, biology - "New Jersey"; Moody, 1875: 96, biology - "Massachusetts"; Planchard, 1875: 96, biology - "Massachusetts"; Andrews, 1875: 80 - "Maryland"; Riley, 1880: 239, biology; Harrington, 1881: 33; Packard, 1881: 162, 226, 236, biology; Riley, 1883: 259, biology; Bates, 1885: 277 - North America. Mexico, Morelia, Las Vigas; Schwarz, 1886a: 29, biology; 1886b, 27, biology; Horn, 1886: 138; Mann, 1886: 27; Holland, 1888: 91 - "British Columbia"; Riley & Howard, 1889: 190, biology; Townsend, 1889: 233 - "the Lower peninsula of Michigan"; 1895: 48 - "New Mexico"; Packard, 1890: 704, 830, 862, biology; Hopkins, 1893: 195, biology; 1899: 439, biology; 1904: 37, biology - "the Louisiana Purchase Exposition St. Louis, Mo."; Chittenden, 1893: 248, biology; Hanham, 1894: 352 - "Quebec"; Slosson, 1894 - "Mount Washington (New Hampshire)"; 1896: 263 - "in alpine region of Mt. Washington"; Chittenden, 1895: 419; Keen, 1895: 219 - "British Columbia"; Laurent, 1895: 323 - "Maine"; Evans, 1895: 173 - "Ontario"; Beutenmüller, 1896: 77 - North America; Wickham, 1897b: 170 - Canada: "Ontario and Quebec"; Warren, 1899: 296 - "Tioga County, Pennsylvania"; Smith, 1900: 291 - "in New Jersey"; 1910: 330 - "New Jersey"; Fall, 1901: 148 - "southern California"; Ulke, 1903: 26, 50 - "District of Columbia"; Felt, 1903: 492, biology - "Albany, Lansingburgh"; Felt, 1906: 335, 339, 349, 366, biology; Wenzel, 1905: 159 - "New Jersey"; Fall & Cockerell, 1907: 193 - "New Mexico"; Morris, 1908: 443, biology; 1916:19 - "Port Hope District"; Blatchley, 1910: 1048 - "in Indiana"; Fisher & Kirk, 1912: 312 - "Harrisburg, Pennsylvania"; Engelhardt, 1912: 221 -

M.A. Lazarev

“Long Island”; Chagnon, 1917: 233 - “Province of Quebec”; Woodruff, 1917: 85 - Lakehurst, New Jersey; 1939: 86 - “Laurentide Provincial Park, Montmorency County, Québec”; Hess, 1917: 64, 67, 68, larva; 1920: 367, biology; Nicolay, 1917: 94 - “Maine”; 1919: 68, biology - “Long Island”; Garnett, 1918: 212 - “California”; Britton, 1920: 267 - “Connecticut”; Craighead, 1923: 88, larva; Munding, 1924: 316 - “Cranberry Lake region, New York”; Essig, 1926: 451 - “New Mexico, Colorado, California, Nevada, Oregon, Washington, British Columbia, Alaska and all the Western States”; Kirk & Knoll, 1926: 23 - “Pennsylvania”; Fletcher, 1926: 143 - “Lloyd-Cornell Reservation”; Hardy, 1926: 4 - “Vancouver Island”; 1927: C24, biology; 1955: B50 - “Vancouver Island, British Columbia”; Hardy & Preece, 1926: 35 - “from the southern portion of Vancouver Island, B.C.”; Procter, 1927: 111 - “Mount Desert Region”; 1946: 177, biology; Tanner, 1927: 33; 1928: 277 - “Zion National Park, Utah”; Leonard, 1928: 437 - “Staten Island, Long Island”; Keen, 1929: 64 - California; Pack, 1930: 219 - “Utah”; Beaulne, 1932: 198 - “Canada”; Ingles, 1933: 59, biology; Wolcott & Montgomery, 1933: 155, biology; Easterling, 1934: 131, 135, 140 - “in Southeastern Ohio”; Mank, 1934: 80 - “Glacier Park, Montana”; DeLeon, 1934: 57; Herrick, 1935: 251; Knowlton & Thatcher, 1936: 279; Lange, 1937: 173 - “California”; Brimley, 1938: 211 - “North Carolina”; Savely, 1939: 333, biology; Parmelee, 1941: 377 - “Michigan”; Löding, 1945: 116 - “Alabama”; Jaques, 1951: 254; Ross, 1967: 24, biology - “British Columbia”; 1968: 11, biology - “British Columbia”.

Hargium lineatum, Kirby, 1837: 178 - “Latitude 54°, Massachusetts”.

Rhagium investigator, Mannerheim, 1852: 367 - “insula Sithka”

Rhagium minutum, Chevrolat, 1851: 664 - “Etats-Unis”.

Rhagium inquisitor, Maeklin, 1857: 186 - “Sithka”; Fauvel, 1889: 150, part. - “Amérique du Nord jusqu'au Mexique. Europe, Sibérie, Japon”; Hamilton, 1894a: 31 - “Alaska”; 1894b: 396, part. - North America, northern Asia and Europe; 1895: 338 - “southwestern Pennsylvania”; Blackwelder, 1946: 573, part. - “[Old World]”; Gardiner, 1957: 251, larva - “Ontario”; Tyson, 1966: 206 - “California”; Gardiner, 1966: 209; 1970: 286, biology - “Ontario, Quebec”; Linsley & Chemsak, 1972: 85 - “Holarctic, boreal in North America”; Perry, 1975: 59 - “Virginia”; Kirk & Balsbaugh, 1975: 98 - “South Dakota”; Gosling & Gosling, 1976: 5 - Michigan; Laliberté & al., 1977: 97, biology - “Québec”; Skiles, 1978: 14 - “Los Angeles County, California”; Gosling, 1986: 157 - “northern Michigan”; Drouin, 1991: 175 - “Québec”; Chemsak & al., 1992: 100 - “borNAmer, México”; MacRae, 1993: 238 - Missouri; Pesarini & Sabbadini, 1995: 68, part. - “Europa, Africa settentrionale, Asia temperata, Nordamerica”; Monné, 1995: 31 - “Holarctic, boreal in North America”; Noguera & Chemsak, 1996: 403 - “Michoacán”; Linsley & Chemsak, 1997: 428; Peck & Thomas, 1998: 120 - Florida; Allison & al., 2000: 4 - North America; Vlasák & Vlasakova, 2002: 207 - “Massachusetts”; Chemsak, 2005: 119 - “boreal in North America”; Costello & al., 2013: 151 - USA (South Dakota): Black Hills; Bousquet & al., 2017: 104- “from the Alexander Archipelago in

M.A. Lazarev

- southeastern Alaska to Newfoundland, as far north as central Yukon Territory”; Haack, 2020: 76 - “Michigan (Drummond Island): Chippewa County”; Chapman & al., 2023: 64 - USA (Kentucky).
- Hargium [Rhagium] lineatum*, Bethune, 1872: 96 “in Lat. 54°, in the province of Massachusetts.”.
- Rhagium lineatus*, Leng, 1890: 65.
- Rhagium (Allorhagium) inquisitor*, Bedel, 1906: 291, part. - “djabal Babor. Europe, Asie jusqu'au Japon, Amérique jusqu'au Mexique”; Planet, 1924: 109, part. - “Europe, Asie et Amérique du Nord”.
- Rhagium (Hargium) inquisitor* var. *lineatum*, Aurivillius, 1912: 165 - “Nordamerika”; Boppe, 1921: 38 - “Amérique septentrionale”.
- Rhagium (Hargium) californicum* Casey, 1913: 195 - “California (Sacramento Co.)”; Lingafelter & al., 2014: 35, 369, lectotype.
- Rhagium (Hargium) crassipes* Casey, 1913: 195 - “Massachusetts (Medford)”; Lingafelter & al., 2014: 47, holotype.
- Rhagium (Hargium) parvicorne* Casey, 1913: 195 - “Massachusetts (Maiden)”; Lingafelter & al., 2014: 296, holotype.
- Rhagium (Hargium) boreale* Casey, 1913: 195 - “Wisconsin (Bayfield), - Wickham”; Lingafelter & al., 2014: 31, holotype.
- Rhagium (Hargium) cariniventre* Casey, 1913: 196 - “Massachusetts and Pennsylvania”; Podaný, 1964: 33; Lingafelter & al., 2014: 37, 369, lectotype.
- Rhagium (Hargium) thoracicum* Casey, 1913: 196 - “New Mexico”; Lingafelter & al., 2014: 333, holotype.
- Rhagium (Hargium) lineatum*, Casey, 1913: 196 - “North-eastern States”; Podaný, 1964: 23.
- Rhagium (Hargium) montanum* Casey, 1913: 197 - “Colorado (Fraser 8000 feet and in Boulder Co.) and New Mexico (Las Vegas)”; Podaný, 1964: 31; Lingafelter & al., 2014: 101, 369, lectotype.
- Rhagium (Hargium) mexicanum* Casey, 1913: 197 - “Mexico (Guerrero)”; Blackwelder, 1946: 573 - “México”; Podaný, 1964: 35; Lingafelter & al., 2014: 98, 369, lectotype.
- Rhagium (Hargium) canadense* Podaný, 1964: 30 - “Marming Par, BC, 4000””; Ulmen & al., 2010: 12
- Rhagium (Hargium) americanum* Podaný, 1964: 32 - “N. Amer.”
- Rhagium (Hargium) quadricostatum* Podaný, 1964: 34 - “Fort Smith, NWT”.
- Stenocorus lineatum*, Canova, 1936: 131 - “Oregon”; Leech, 1947: 108 - “British Columbia”.
- Stenocorus inquisitor*, Hopping, 1937: 9 - “...America North of Mexico”; Knull, 1946: 174 - “Ohio”; Fattig, 1947: 13 - “Georgia” (U.S. state); Hardy, 1948: 32 - “Manning Park, British Columbia”; Knowlton & Wood, 1950: 11 - “Utah”; Howden & Vogt, 1951: 591 - “Coastal Plain of Maryland”; Beal & al., 1952: 110, biology - “Piedmont Plateau of North Carolina”; Thomas, 1955: 340, biology; Dillon & Dillon, 1961: 618 - North America; Wilson, 1971: 61, biology - “New England”; Hatch, 1971: 138 - “Pacific Northwest”.
- Rhagium inquisitor* var. *lineatum*, Blackwelder, 1946: 573 (= *investigator* Mannh.) - “México, U. S. A.”; Duffy, 1960: 74 - Mexico, U.S.A., Canada.

M.A. Lazarev

- Rhagium (Hargium) inquisitor*, Duffy, 1953: 127, larva - imported from North America.
Stenocorus inquisitor lineatus, Baker, 1972: 206, biology.
Rhagium papayanum Podaný, 1978: 4 - “Mexique”; Zaragoza-Caballero & Pérez-Hernández, 2017: 38 - “Mexico: Estado de México, Río Frío, Papayo”.
- Rhagium mexicanum nigra* Podaný, 1978: 4 - “Mexique”.
- Rhagium* (s. str.) *inquisitor*, Villiers, 1978: 80, part. - “France, Europe, Afrique du Nord, Sibérie occidentale. Amerique du Nord, Caucase, Asie mineure”; Vives, 2000: 216, part. - “paleártica y Norteamérica”; 2001: 115, part. - “paleártica, alcanza la zona boreal norteamericana”.
- Rhagium inquisitor inquisitor*, Monné & Giesbert, 1994: 169 - “Holarctic: NAmer (boreal regions)”; Schiefer, 1998: 121 - “Mississippi”; Heffern, 1998: 9, part. - “AK, AL, AZ, CA, CO, CT, FL, GA, ID, IN, MA, MD, ME, MI, MS, MT, NC, NJ, NM, NY, OH, OK, OR, PA, SC, SD, TX, UT, WA, WI, AB, BC, MB, NB, NF, NT, ON, PQ, SK, YK Mexico, Europe, Asia”; Holt, 2013: 245 - “Alabama”; Klingeman & al., 2017: 296 - “Tennessee”; Rice & al., 2017: 670 - “Idaho”; Lagos Ordoñez & Nápoles, 2024: 43 - “Canadá, EUA, México (Guerrero, México, Michoacán, Puebla)”; Martínez-Hernández & al., 2024: 189 - “Mexico (Oaxaca): Oaxaca, Santiago Xiacui”.
- Rhagium canadense*, Ulmen & al., 2010: 12.

Type locality. Northern America.

Temples narrower than eyes, smooth and shining; antennae thick and short; slightly surpassing elytral bases; prothorax wide, elytra with variable sculpture and color strongly carinated; abdomen often partly yellow; body length: 16.0-20.0 mm.

Distribution. About whole territory of North America, from Mexico to Alaska and Canada.

Bionomy. Larvae develop under the bark of coniferous trees (*Picea*, *Pinus*, *Larix*, *Tsuga*, *Pseudotsuga* and others); the generation lasts 2 years. Imagoes active from February to July

***Rhagium inquisitor sudeticum* Plavilstshikov, 1936, rest. nom.**

Figs 3-4

Rhagium inquisitor inquisitor var. *sudetica* Plavilstshikov, 1915: 46 [unavailable name] - “Monts Sudètes”.

Rhagium inquisitor var. *sudeticum* Plavilstshikov, 1936: 143, 504.

Rhagium inquisitor var. *sudetica*, Danilevsky, 2009: 690, type material is not found.

Type locality. Sudeten Mountains or Sudetes.

M.A. Lazarev

According to the original description, antennae much shorter and thinner, than in the nominative subspecies; prothorax longer and narrower; elytra narrower at shoulders, with poorly developed carinae, without wrinkles or with poor wrinkles, with very poor punctation, pale-yellow or ash-grey color; anterior elytral belt absent or hardly pronounced; post middle elytral belt distinct; body length 10.0-12.0 mm.

Material. 1 male, 1 female, Italy, Romagna, 15.8.1975 - MD; 5 males, 3 females, Italy, Veneto, Treviso, Vittorio Veneto, Crodarossa, 14-31.5.1983, L. Costelo leg. - ML; 1 male, Croatia, 26.6.1981 - MD; 2 males, 1 female, Germany, Pfalz, Daun, 12.1975, Schimmel leg. - MD; 2 males, Bulgaria, Pirin, 2.7.1987, 11.8.1987, V. Sakalyan leg. - MD; 1 female, Bulgaria, Sofia, 10.6.2007, T. Ljubomirov leg. - MD.

Distribution. I don't know the type specimens (are not available in Plavilstshikov's collection), but several my series totally agree with the original description: Croatia, Italy, Bulgaria, Germany.

Bionomy. Larvae usually develop under the bark of coniferous trees (*Picea*, *Pinuss*, *Abie*, *Larix*), but sometimes in deciduous trees (*Betula*); the generation lasts 2 years. Imagoes active from April to June.

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Figs 1-2. *Rhagium inquisitor inquisitor* (Linnaeus, 1758). 1. male, Russia, Moscow Region, Udelnaya, 3.4.2010, M. Danilevsky leg.; 2. female, Kazakhstan, 15 km S Almaty, Butakovka, 1600 m, 1.6.2002, M. Danilevsky leg.

Figs 3-4. *Rhagium inquisitor sudeticum* Plavilstshikov, 1936, **rest. nom.**: 3. male, Italy, Romagna, 15.8.1975; 4. female with the same label.

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M.A. Lazarev

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M.A. Lazarev

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***Akimerus schaefferi dentipes* (Mulsant, 1842) rest. nom. from
France and *Etorofus pubescens minetti* ssp. nov. from France
(Coleoptera: Cerambycidae)**

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Key words: Cerambycidae, Coleoptera, taxonomy, new subspecies, restored name, Europe.

Abstract. *Akimerus schaefferi dentipes* (Mulsant, 1842) **rest. nom.** was compared with *A. s. schaefferi* (Laicharting, 1784), *A. s. ariannae* Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2007, *A. berchmansii* Breit, 1915, and *Etorofus pubescens minetti* **ssp. nov.** was compared with *E. p. pubescens* (Fabricius, 1787).

Materials and methods

Acronyms of collections:

JV - collection of J. Vartanis (Uherský Brod, Czech Republic);

ML - collection of M.A. Lazarev (Moscow, Russia);

MS - collection of M. Sláma (Praha, Czechia);

RM - collection of R. Minetti (France).

Results

***Akimerus schaefferi dentipes* (Mulsant, 1842) rest. nom.**

Plate 1

Body stocky, antennae thick, slightly shorter than the body. Third to fifth antennomeres strongly knotted and widened at the end. Pronotum with two large bumps on the surface, coarsely wrinkled and dotted, with a longitudinal groove in the middle. Elytra in females, only about 2.5 times longer than wide at the base, very strongly narrowed posteriorly, more finely wrinkled at the base. Females reddish-yellow, abdominal sternite densely golden-yellow hairy.

J. Vartanis

Elytra in females very sparsely hairy, seemingly bare, without a visible yellow transverse band at its apex in the middle (see photograph), a very different character from the typical species *A. s. schaefferi* (Laicharting, 1784). In males, the elytra are very narrow, up to 3.5 times longer than wide at the base, orange-yellow (see photo), these two visible features are very different from the typical species *A. s. schaefferi* (Laicharting, 1784). The species is currently found only in France.

Body size: males 18-22 mm, females 23-26 mm.

Differential diagnosis. The new subspecies *A. s. dentipes* (Mulsant, 1842) **rest. nom.** occurs so far in France, where from book sources from French colleagues, this species occurs very rarely, mainly on trees (*Quercus*), and is captured individually and rarely in various localities. Very characteristic features for this new subspecies are mainly in females, where the transverse yellow band in the middle of the elytron is missing, as can be seen in the photo below. Males show the color of the elytron more orange-yellow, are slimmer and at the base are 3.55x wider than the length of the elytron. It was compared with the species *A. s. schaefferi* (Laicharting, 1784), which occurs mainly in Central Europe (Czech Republic, Slovakia, Austria, Germany, Ukraine, Hungary and some destinations in the Balkans), the species occurs very rarely in native forests (*Quercus*). Females are reddish-brown, with a transverse yellow band in the middle of the elytron. Males are more stocky, the width of the shoulders at the base is only 3 times longer than the length of the elytron. In Greece, another endemic species occurs, *A. s. ariannae* Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2007, where females are reddish-brown to completely black with a characteristic yellow transverse band in the middle of the elytron. In males, the width of the shoulders at the base is only 3 times longer than the length of the elytron. The last species *A. berchmansii* Breit, 1915, is found only in Turkey, at first glance a very different species, where the females are mostly all black, and show a very distinct, bordered, yellow longitudinal band in the middle of the elytron. The males are half all black, or dark red with a black vertical band on the elytron.

Plate - 1

J. Vartanis

A new subspecies from France, *A. s. dentipes* (Mulsant, 1842) **rest. nom.** shows very distinctive features for a new subspecies, which in biological systematics is a subspecies taxon denoting individual with their own morphological characters that differ from another subspecies of the same species.

Material. 1 female, France, Deblois, 20.VII.1996, Auvray lgt. - JV; 3 females, France, Deblois, VII.1998, lgt. Auvray - MS; 1 male, 1 female, France, de Blois, 19.VII.1994, N. Auvray leg. - ML; 1 female, France - 41000, Blois St. Sulpice env, 100 m, 47.60°N 01.26°E, 15.7.1996, C. Auvray leg. - ML; 1 male, France, Aiguines Forêt de Margés, 3.VIII.1979, P.Berger lgt. - MS; 1 male, France, Aiguines, 7.VII. 2018, J.Steinhofer lgt. - MS; 1 male, 1 female, France, Ft. De Morieves, VI.2004, Pascala Stefani lgt. - MS; 1 male, 2 females France - MS; 5 males, France, Forêt Domaniale de Russy, VII. 1998, Minetti lgt. - JV; 2 males, 3 females, France, Molineuf, 6.VII.1992, Machard lgt.; 4 males, France, Ft. De Boulogne, 12.VII.1996 - RM.

Species distribution.

1. *Akimerus schaefferi schaefferi* (Laicharting, 1784): Austria, Czechia, Slovakia, Ukraina, Hungary, Croatia, Germany, Polonia, Romania.
2. *Akimerus schaefferi ariannae* Pesarini & Sabbadini, 2007: Greece.
3. *Akimerus berchmansii* Breit, 1915: Turkey.
4. *Akimerus schaefferi dentipes* (Mulsant, 1842) **rest. nom.** France.

Bionomics. The occurrence of the subspecies is always dependent on the presence of very old *Quercus*, or *Quercet* of stump origin. In warm weather, the adults fly around the crowns and in the crowns of trees, perching on the leaves of the trees.

J. Vartanis

***Etorofus pubescens minetti* ssp. nov.**

Plate 2

Pronotum black, very densely granular with long, dense golden pubescence, which is very long. Antennae dark brown to black, 3rd antennomeres in both males and females, shorter than 4th and 5th antennomeres together. 4th and 5th antennomeres are 1.76x together longer than 3rd antennomeres. Elytra yellow, very densely granular, gaps smaller than dots themselves, very long adjacent pubescence. Length of elytron is 2.9x longer than at base wide. This is a very narrow, long species, compared to the nominal form. Abdominal sternite, very sparsely pubescent, almost glabrous. Pieces from France show very different characters, for a new subspecies *Etorofus pubescens minetti* ssp. nov.

Body size: males 13-15 mm, females 15-17 mm.

Material. Holotype, male, France, Val d'Escrin, Vars (04), 29.VI.2001, R. Minetti lgt. - JV; 60 Paratypes: 8 males, 6 females, France, Val d'Escrin, Vars (04), 29.VI.2001, R. Minetti lgt. - JV, RM; 5 males, 5 females, France, Col du Labouret, 4.VII. 2015 , R. Minetti lgt. - JV, RM; 5 males, 4 females, France, Col du Labouret, 27.VI.2001, R.Minetti lgt. - JV, RM; 7 males, 3 females, France, Chateau Queyras, VII.1999 - JV, RM; 3 males, 2 females, VII.2004 - JV, RM; 2 males, 7.VII.1961- JV, RM; 4 males, 1 female, France, Coulloubroux, VII.1987 - JV, RM; 3 males, 2 females, France, Col de Vars, 4.VII.2014 - 1.VII.2018, R.Minetti lgt. - JV, RM.

Differential diagnosis: The specimens of the new species, so far endemic to France, *E. p. minetti* ssp. nov., show very different characters, characteristic of the new subspecies. I have listed the different characters in the description and also documented them in the photograph on plate number 2. There are many specimens in the collections. *E. p. pubescens* (Fabricius, 1787) (Czechia, Slovakia, Austria, Balkán, Greece), pronotum black, very sparsely granular with short golden pubescence, which is shorter than in the new species *E. p. minetti* ssp. nov. Antennae dark brown, 3rd antennomeres in both males and females, very long, almost as long as 4th and 5th antennomeres together. 4th and 5th antennomeres are only 1.33 times longer together than 3rd antennomeres.

Plate - 2

J. Vartanis

Elytra yellow, very finely, gaps larger than dots themselves, very short and sparsely adjacent pubescence. Length of elytron 2.6 times longer than at base wide. This is a less narrow species, compared to the new species. Abdominal sternite, very densely, long adjacent pubescence. Pieces of the species *E. p. pubescens*, from different areas and destinations in Europe show very different characters, compared to the new subspecies *E. p. minetti* **ssp. nov.**

Bionomics. Development in coniferous trees, imago on flowers, 6th-7th month.

Etymology. The new subspecies *Etorofus pubescens minetti* **ssp. nov.**, received its name from the French colleague R. Minetti, who discovered this species in several locations in France.

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Содержание // Contents

Данилевский М.Л. Два новых подвида <i>Alosterna tabacicolor</i> (DeGeer, 1775) (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) с Дальнего Востока России Danilevsky M.L. Two new subspecies of <i>Alosterna tabacicolor</i> (DeGeer, 1775) (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) from the Far East of Russia.....	238
Хава И. Описание самца <i>Globicornis (Hadrotoma) semilimbata</i> (Pic, 1906) (Coleoptera: Dermestidae: Megatominae) Háva J. A description of the male of <i>Globicornis (Hadrotoma) semilimbata</i> (Pic, 1906) (Coleoptera: Dermestidae: Megatominae)..	246
Лазарев М.А. Восстановлены два подвидовых названия <i>Rhagium inquisitor</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) из Центральной Европы и Северной Америки (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) Lazarev M.A. Two subspecies names of <i>Rhagium inquisitor</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) from Central Europe and North America (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) are restored.....	252
Вартанис Я. <i>Akimerus schaefferi dentipes</i> (Mulsant, 1842) rest. nom. из Франции и <i>Etorofus pubescens minetti ssp. nov.</i> из Франции France (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) Vartanis J. <i>Akimerus schaefferi dentipes</i> (Mulsant, 1842) rest. nom. from France and <i>Etorofus pubescens minetti ssp. nov.</i> from France (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae).....	285
О ЖУРНАЛЕ / ABOUT THE JOURNAL	292